

Supplementary table S4. Information of the differentially expressed genes at PP of the wild type (WT) and the mutant (MU).

	GeneID	$\log_2$ (FPKM_MU/FPKM_WT)	P-value
Up regulated in MU			
	BMSK0010020.1	11.3708	0.0000
	BMSK0000962.1	10.5521	0.0000
	BMSK0004217.1	5.8954	0.0000
	BMSK0000966.1	6.2357	0.0000
	BMSK0013673.1	2.3102	0.0000
	BMSK0008956.1	3.3175	0.0000
	BMSK0000963.1	8.8145	0.0000
	BMSK0005309.1	5.9132	0.0000
	BMSK0004212.1	9.4273	0.0000
	BMSK0004222.1	9.3293	0.0000
	BMSK0000965.1	7.6036	0.0000
	BMSK0000961.1	8.7176	0.0000
	BMSK0006067.1	1.3966	0.0001
	BMSK0008976.1	3.1453	0.0002
	BMSK0005285.1	2.0450	0.0002
	BMSK0004221.1	6.2882	0.0002
	BMSK0010119.1	6.4739	0.0005
	BMSK0000964.1	6.9642	0.0007
	BMSK0008962.1	2.4478	0.0007
	BMSK0001553.1	3.8120	0.0014
	BMSK0006093.1	5.5059	0.0019
	BMSK0006068.1	4.1743	0.0019
	BMSK0013320.1	2.1262	0.0024
	BMSK0006092.1	3.5302	0.0026
	BMSK0007677.1	1.6532	0.0027
	BMSK0005318.1	2.0366	0.0029
	BMSK0007935.1	5.8137	0.0035
	BMSK0001065.1	6.1252	0.0038
	BMSK0006197.1	4.1631	0.0044
	BMSK0003921.1	3.5589	0.0050
	BMSK0003119.1	1.1243	0.0063
	BMSK0015955.1	4.6741	0.0068
	BMSK0006005.1	3.3509	0.0074
	BMSK0010486.1	1.5325	0.0078
	BMSK0001375.1	5.0941	0.0081
	BMSK0004226.1	1.9695	0.0082
	BMSK0009693.1	2.7965	0.0084
	BMSK0007482.1	1.1257	0.0086
	BMSK0010136.1	2.1610	0.0091
	BMSK0005297.1	1.2792	0.0094
	BMSK0010109.1	2.9501	0.0104
	BMSK0005148.1	6.8509	0.0108
	BMSK0002359.1	1.2435	0.0118
	BMSK0012015.1	5.0916	0.0120
	BMSK0006770.1	2.8063	0.0124
	BMSK0005299.1	1.0415	0.0126
	BMSK0006069.1	3.9686	0.0129
	BMSK0003471.1	6.5626	0.0135
	BMSK0013598.1	1.9000	0.0138
	BMSK0010026.1	3.1953	0.0141
	BMSK0009007.1	1.7169	0.0157
	BMSK0009784.1	1.3323	0.0167
	BMSK0001959.1	1.4929	0.0172
	BMSK0002361.1	3.9938	0.0177
	BMSK0001198.1	2.6486	0.0179
	BMSK0011871.1	1.5677	0.0219
	BMSK0010886.1	3.9014	0.0225
	BMSK0006771.1	1.9572	0.0229
	BMSK0001960.1	1.3812	0.0240
	BMSK0012037.1	1.2968	0.0242

BMSK0010165.1	1.4481	0.0242
BMSK0006840.1	1.2169	0.0251
BMSK0010227.1	4.9292	0.0254
BMSK0000521.1	3.4742	0.0259
BMSK0009892.1	1.7479	0.0261
BMSK0004108.1	2.7007	0.0261
BMSK0005295.1	1.6885	0.0261
BMSK0006030.1	1.0605	0.0262
BMSK0010135.1	1.5422	0.0262
BMSK0015546.1	2.9136	0.0268
BMSK0005762.1	2.5643	0.0280
BMSK0008761.1	3.0211	0.0285
BMSK0001833.1	3.2010	0.0286
BMSK0006801.1	1.6871	0.0286
BMSK0012036.1	2.9473	0.0290
BMSK0011794.1	2.2869	0.0292
BMSK0009406.1	1.2453	0.0297
BMSK0006055.1	1.2166	0.0306
BMSK0005279.1	1.4582	0.0308
BMSK0013761.1	2.5126	0.0309
BMSK0009447.1	4.6409	0.0320
BMSK0009601.1	1.0283	0.0322
BMSK0011989.1	1.9024	0.0346
BMSK0006266.1	1.9803	0.0347
BMSK0015775.1	3.9049	0.0365
BMSK0012500.1	2.9021	0.0366
BMSK0008557.1	1.3450	0.0368
BMSK0007660.1	2.2528	0.0375
BMSK0007862.1	1.3860	0.0403
BMSK0002346.1	1.5837	0.0405
BMSK0005654.1	1.9725	0.0409
BMSK0014196.1	5.1630	0.0415
BMSK0013383.1	1.2158	0.0422
BMSK0015774.1	3.9424	0.0425
BMSK0002363.1	2.5469	0.0426
BMSK0011143.1	2.0828	0.0438
BMSK0012194.1	1.6152	0.0449
BMSK0011772.1	1.5902	0.0453
BMSK0001884.1	3.0448	0.0456
BMSK0002172.1	1.2540	0.0468
BMSK0007354.1	4.0529	0.0481
BMSK0009899.1	3.4307	0.0489

Down regulated in MU

BMSK0002347	-2.3113	0.0000
BMSK0000953	-9.0223	0.0000
BMSK0007371	-8.4489	0.0000
BMSK0015391	-6.9681	0.0000
BMSK0008035	-8.8904	0.0000
BMSK0005276	-2.7392	0.0000
BMSK0000710	-5.5143	0.0001
BMSK0013794	-4.6147	0.0001
BMSK0013391	-4.0446	0.0001
BMSK0010658	-5.9636	0.0001
BMSK0013317	-7.6886	0.0002
BMSK0010144	-3.8108	0.0002
BMSK0014671	-2.0539	0.0003
BMSK0010462	-4.7809	0.0003
BMSK0011303	-2.1263	0.0004
BMSK0005497	-4.7839	0.0004
BMSK0015877	-6.1345	0.0005
BMSK0002197	-5.4342	0.0005
BMSK0009213	-7.7351	0.0006
BMSK0001149	-3.9510	0.0006

BMSK0013295	-1.6707	0.0008
BMSK0010779	-5.6798	0.0008
BMSK0001515	-6.0104	0.0008
BMSK0003940	-3.9664	0.0008
BMSK0000266	-7.5557	0.0009
BMSK0008951	-3.6353	0.0010
BMSK0000956	-4.4100	0.0011
BMSK0004249	-1.9427	0.0012
BMSK0006037	-1.6796	0.0012
BMSK0014768	-8.7736	0.0012
BMSK0010268	-4.2861	0.0013
BMSK0006789	-7.2541	0.0013
BMSK0008998	-4.4951	0.0013
BMSK0007693	-2.3850	0.0014
BMSK0012073	-2.3627	0.0015
BMSK0006062	-3.4468	0.0017
BMSK0011439	-2.3000	0.0021
BMSK0002165	-4.7984	0.0022
BMSK0010262	-1.9427	0.0023
BMSK0008903	-4.8987	0.0023
BMSK0008253	-2.0616	0.0023
BMSK0007560	-4.8585	0.0026
BMSK0005503	-5.1098	0.0026
BMSK0011877	-4.4185	0.0027
BMSK0015680	-3.4494	0.0027
BMSK0006980	-3.7839	0.0027
BMSK0002213	-2.4659	0.0027
BMSK0007609	-4.5033	0.0028
BMSK0004902	-4.8274	0.0028
BMSK0015767	-4.8248	0.0031
BMSK0013626	-2.9004	0.0032
BMSK0011973	-4.3186	0.0036
BMSK0014122	-2.6481	0.0037
BMSK0006035	-3.3260	0.0037
BMSK0010444	-5.7280	0.0038
BMSK0012315	-7.7437	0.0040
BMSK0015393	-5.6158	0.0040
BMSK0000161	-5.9394	0.0042
BMSK0012995	-6.4857	0.0043
BMSK0012537	-4.4419	0.0043
BMSK0002900	-3.2551	0.0044
BMSK0004651	-3.1356	0.0044
BMSK0000376	-6.3342	0.0044
BMSK0001855	-7.0955	0.0044
BMSK0014613	-8.0938	0.0046
BMSK0008063	-5.8621	0.0046
BMSK0014151	-3.0535	0.0047
BMSK0004684	-2.8759	0.0048
BMSK0000576	-2.1980	0.0048
BMSK0008317	-5.4078	0.0049
BMSK0000952	-2.4592	0.0052
BMSK0004778	-4.3076	0.0052
BMSK0000128	-3.7269	0.0053
BMSK0013994	-3.8127	0.0054
BMSK0008633	-3.4160	0.0054
BMSK0011078	-2.8537	0.0057
BMSK0010890	-1.3584	0.0058
BMSK0014666	-1.6726	0.0059
BMSK0000117	-3.8576	0.0059
BMSK0000127	-4.3763	0.0061
BMSK0014791	-5.1743	0.0061
BMSK0008006	-3.5846	0.0061
BMSK0005277	-4.0584	0.0065

BMSK0006300	-3.9339	0.0067
BMSK0002240	-1.2986	0.0068
BMSK0004848	-4.4061	0.0069
BMSK0001903	-3.3367	0.0069
BMSK0002121	-1.1832	0.0069
BMSK0000503	-5.2722	0.0070
BMSK0013405	-2.9728	0.0071
BMSK0004841	-4.1000	0.0072
BMSK0003142	-3.7220	0.0073
BMSK0014619	-2.2283	0.0075
BMSK0000108	-3.6385	0.0076
BMSK0003073	-4.9834	0.0076
BMSK0010889	-4.9744	0.0079
BMSK0001864	-5.2006	0.0082
BMSK0008797	-3.3240	0.0086
BMSK0005581	-1.5501	0.0086
BMSK0015392	-5.1360	0.0088
BMSK0001054	-2.9101	0.0089
BMSK0003913	-2.0627	0.0091
BMSK0001593	-5.3512	0.0093
BMSK0003626	-6.0393	0.0095
BMSK0008971	-1.8341	0.0096
BMSK0003511	-2.4012	0.0098
BMSK0005882	-3.7914	0.0099
BMSK0005651	-4.4307	0.0100
BMSK0011526	-4.6964	0.0102
BMSK0000495	-7.0122	0.0102
BMSK0006215	-3.4194	0.0102
BMSK0000292	-4.7668	0.0104
BMSK0009828	-3.4158	0.0104
BMSK0012279	-5.1134	0.0106
BMSK0015127	-1.5124	0.0106
BMSK0014605	-6.4965	0.0108
BMSK0015917	-3.9722	0.0109
BMSK0009186	-3.6857	0.0110
BMSK0006755	-2.9340	0.0110
BMSK0012088	-4.5614	0.0111
BMSK0008115	-2.9739	0.0111
BMSK0014668	-4.2141	0.0111
BMSK0015791	-6.3606	0.0113
BMSK0011036	-1.9785	0.0116
BMSK0013053	-6.7936	0.0117
BMSK0008815	-4.8721	0.0118
BMSK0002681	-3.1054	0.0118
BMSK0011177	-1.4616	0.0119
BMSK0013818	-3.6072	0.0120
BMSK0014245	-5.8222	0.0120
BMSK0005429	-4.2444	0.0121
BMSK0000420	-1.5683	0.0121
BMSK0006683	-5.0454	0.0122
BMSK0003350	-5.5995	0.0122
BMSK0011543	-4.6930	0.0123
BMSK0006323	-2.4392	0.0125
BMSK0012380	-3.0422	0.0125
BMSK0014335	-1.9387	0.0126
BMSK0000130	-7.0373	0.0128
BMSK0014201	-1.9541	0.0129
BMSK0003433	-3.5445	0.0129
BMSK0002305	-2.9758	0.0130
BMSK0008824	-1.5604	0.0130
BMSK0004493	-2.8324	0.0131
BMSK0006063	-5.0991	0.0133
BMSK0010532	-1.3903	0.0133

BMSK0012894	-4.2236	0.0134
BMSK0013392	-3.7300	0.0135
BMSK0009050	-4.1126	0.0136
BMSK0014381	-2.0013	0.0136
BMSK0007626	-2.7904	0.0137
BMSK0006247	-1.4783	0.0139
BMSK0003210	-6.1882	0.0140
BMSK0014414	-6.1666	0.0140
BMSK0015948	-4.8692	0.0141
BMSK0002239	-5.2241	0.0142
BMSK0005358	-6.7700	0.0143
BMSK0010402	-2.4388	0.0144
BMSK0005331	-2.1247	0.0145
BMSK0011525	-6.8080	0.0146
BMSK0002659	-7.0671	0.0148
BMSK0007514	-3.1524	0.0149
BMSK0010495	-5.4030	0.0151
BMSK0015295	-1.6438	0.0152
BMSK0006909	-4.6298	0.0153
BMSK0014558	-2.1892	0.0154
BMSK0012933	-4.4719	0.0156
BMSK0005458	-3.0627	0.0157
BMSK0008107	-3.9032	0.0159
BMSK0000858	-4.3959	0.0160
BMSK0011449	-2.6710	0.0161
BMSK0009261	-2.4721	0.0162
BMSK0008421	-2.7689	0.0162
BMSK0009789	-6.8300	0.0164
BMSK0006582	-2.8552	0.0164
BMSK0010182	-6.9178	0.0167
BMSK0005498	-3.1484	0.0169
BMSK0015248	-4.4965	0.0171
BMSK0002832	-2.2412	0.0173
BMSK0015925	-4.4941	0.0180
BMSK0006762	-2.8927	0.0181
BMSK0002178	-1.0980	0.0182
BMSK0012827	-1.7949	0.0182
BMSK0006761	-2.2736	0.0185
BMSK0010145	-4.7595	0.0185
BMSK0012660	-2.5777	0.0187
BMSK0008910	-3.1451	0.0188
BMSK0003272	-2.7173	0.0189
BMSK0001463	-5.1470	0.0190
BMSK0010313	-3.4093	0.0192
BMSK0013381	-4.7585	0.0192
BMSK0013485	-1.9955	0.0193
BMSK0003351	-2.4723	0.0193
BMSK0006974	-3.4651	0.0194
BMSK0012338	-2.5314	0.0199
BMSK0013518	-3.0188	0.0200
BMSK0009902	-1.8843	0.0201
BMSK0002214	-3.1893	0.0201
BMSK0003763	-4.9714	0.0203
BMSK0000686	-6.1143	0.0207
BMSK0015035	-2.4001	0.0212
BMSK0014529	-1.7545	0.0215
BMSK0004613	-3.8089	0.0218
BMSK0008727	-5.9748	0.0221
BMSK0013475	-3.0080	0.0223
BMSK0006195	-1.3481	0.0224
BMSK0005177	-2.8169	0.0226
BMSK0004964	-3.3164	0.0230
BMSK0015879	-3.9265	0.0232

BMSK0013793	-4.0056	0.0232
BMSK0007824	-2.5890	0.0233
BMSK0015397	-5.5286	0.0237
BMSK0011429	-5.1709	0.0237
BMSK0008064	-2.1567	0.0238
BMSK0007589	-3.5528	0.0239
BMSK0010659	-2.9545	0.0240
BMSK0013506	-2.0291	0.0244
BMSK0005463	-3.8585	0.0245
BMSK0001041	-1.8078	0.0248
BMSK0006574	-6.5866	0.0250
BMSK0007542	-1.9327	0.0251
BMSK0011962	-2.6908	0.0251
BMSK0005186	-3.3113	0.0251
BMSK0012507	-2.3332	0.0253
BMSK0012502	-2.0813	0.0254
BMSK0002065	-3.7228	0.0257
BMSK0003409	-4.8148	0.0258
BMSK0006194	-2.7850	0.0260
BMSK0008886	-3.7428	0.0260
BMSK0003818	-2.2834	0.0261
BMSK0003823	-2.6582	0.0262
BMSK0015969	-5.3526	0.0264
BMSK0007881	-1.8407	0.0264
BMSK0001183	-2.7453	0.0265
BMSK0011657	-4.8703	0.0266
BMSK0004678	-3.6578	0.0269
BMSK0005494	-1.6154	0.0269
BMSK0003301	-2.9332	0.0271
BMSK0013403	-2.0980	0.0272
BMSK0014270	-2.1292	0.0275
BMSK0007507	-4.7047	0.0281
BMSK0014080	-1.2469	0.0282
BMSK0008432	-5.9093	0.0285
BMSK0015669	-2.9201	0.0287
BMSK0011897	-1.0482	0.0292
BMSK0000332	-5.6424	0.0293
BMSK0014959	-4.9801	0.0296
BMSK0002164	-3.2335	0.0303
BMSK0009595	-2.8962	0.0305
BMSK0005532	-3.3398	0.0306
BMSK0001514	-2.1495	0.0307
BMSK0006675	-3.0887	0.0308
BMSK0000198	-4.6417	0.0312
BMSK0016018	-3.3464	0.0312
BMSK0004209	-2.0369	0.0312
BMSK0015668	-2.3294	0.0315
BMSK0002314	-2.8546	0.0316
BMSK0013412	-2.2803	0.0316
BMSK0007183	-2.2866	0.0318
BMSK0011059	-1.0455	0.0321
BMSK0013199	-3.1190	0.0326
BMSK0013933	-4.3071	0.0326
BMSK0013386	-1.6654	0.0327
BMSK0013208	-1.8477	0.0327
BMSK0011863	-2.0826	0.0332
BMSK0000672	-3.9549	0.0339
BMSK0011082	-1.2964	0.0340
BMSK0015032	-4.3361	0.0341
BMSK0011603	-1.8976	0.0346
BMSK0004329	-1.7008	0.0348
BMSK0014890	-2.7532	0.0350
BMSK0006413	-2.8406	0.0353

BMSK0002170	-1.7166	0.0353
BMSK0006605	-3.3598	0.0355
BMSK0004136	-3.2656	0.0359
BMSK0011903	-1.4343	0.0362
BMSK0000208	-3.6186	0.0364
BMSK0003872	-3.2815	0.0366
BMSK0010083	-3.7142	0.0367
BMSK0010253	-1.9921	0.0367
BMSK0003612	-2.6776	0.0368
BMSK0015638	-2.6840	0.0369
BMSK0000286	-4.9364	0.0375
BMSK0013080	-3.6574	0.0376
BMSK0011902	-2.4950	0.0377
BMSK0008024	-2.2800	0.0379
BMSK0001975	-1.8227	0.0383
BMSK0007339	-1.0427	0.0384
BMSK0003339	-2.6711	0.0386
BMSK0012414	-5.6627	0.0387
BMSK0012998	-4.1429	0.0388
BMSK0012935	-4.7381	0.0391
BMSK0016058	-2.1662	0.0392
BMSK0003679	-1.4160	0.0393
BMSK0007186	-4.2998	0.0394
BMSK0010792	-2.5360	0.0397
BMSK0004156	-2.5780	0.0401
BMSK0002972	-4.6803	0.0402
BMSK0008863	-2.4292	0.0403
BMSK0014475	-3.5047	0.0403
BMSK0007868	-1.7622	0.0404
BMSK0000457	-4.7670	0.0405
BMSK0007715	-3.1372	0.0407
BMSK0010415	-1.3196	0.0409
BMSK0001308	-3.1282	0.0412
BMSK0003672	-5.9824	0.0416
BMSK0003758	-2.0835	0.0417
BMSK0008570	-1.3083	0.0417
BMSK0007884	-2.7798	0.0418
BMSK0005088	-1.1679	0.0419
BMSK0006088	-1.7567	0.0420
BMSK0014480	-1.7767	0.0422
BMSK0001471	-2.9483	0.0423
BMSK0000123	-1.5676	0.0423
BMSK0006575	-1.7034	0.0425
BMSK0013026	-3.7483	0.0426
BMSK0012246	-2.0134	0.0435
BMSK0010357	-3.7922	0.0439
BMSK0002399	-5.7861	0.0442
BMSK0014855	-1.6441	0.0444
BMSK0013758	-4.0846	0.0447
BMSK0014862	-1.4975	0.0449
BMSK0015990	-2.1852	0.0455
BMSK0006763	-2.7541	0.0456
BMSK0006638	-1.2979	0.0460
BMSK0001981	-2.0019	0.0460
BMSK0009396	-3.4385	0.0465
BMSK0009465	-2.1527	0.0466
BMSK0002187	-3.5614	0.0467
BMSK0012283	-5.0784	0.0469
BMSK0002631	-1.2255	0.0470
BMSK0011882	-5.4781	0.0471
BMSK0009734	-2.5683	0.0472
BMSK0008846	-1.4183	0.0474
BMSK0007142	-2.6936	0.0475

BMSK0014664	-2.0471	0.0478
BMSK0008868	-2.1618	0.0480
BMSK0000342	-5.9976	0.0483
BMSK0009722	-2.1780	0.0485
BMSK0001058	-3.9916	0.0490
BMSK0000983	-1.0722	0.0493
BMSK0006338	-2.1526	0.0495
BMSK0003644	-2.8824	0.0497
BMSK0001165	-3.6929	0.0498
